

README

Dataset for “Vatnajökull mass loss under solar geoengineering due to the North Atlantic meridional overturning circulation”

32 model experiments

- Earth System Models: BNU-ESM, HadGEM2-ES, MIROC-ESM, MIROC-ESM-CHEM
- Scenario: Historical (1982-2005), G4 (2020-2089), RCP4.5 (2006-2089), RCP8.5 (2006-2089).
- Variable: Surface mass balance (unit: mm yr⁻¹), Surface runoff of meltwater (mm yr⁻¹)
- Resolution: 0.025°×0.025°/ annual

The data is provided as netCDF files: VIC_SEMIC_SMB.nc,

VIC_SEMIC_RUNOFF.nc, we use:

- {smb, runoff} represent {surface mass balance, surface runoff of meltwater};
- {bnu, hadgem, miroc, chem} represent {BNU-ESM, HadGEM2-ES, MIROC-ESM, MIROC-ESM-CHEM}
- {his, g4, rcp45, rcp85} represent {Historical, G4, RCP4.5, RCP8.5}

If you have any questions for the data, please contact: yuechao.bnu@gmail.com